

FROM INFORMATION DELIVERY TO BRAIN-BASED LEARNING

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We build on the contribution *Why and how Montessori education can improve the development of (not only) a child's language* (Slováček, 2024), which proposed an educational pathway aligned with contemporary pedagogy, developmental neuroscience, and the ontogeny of speech in Slovak-speaking children. Here, we broaden that discussion beyond language to emphasize how Montessori education, through self-directed activity, calibrated feedback, purposeful movement, and rich peer interaction, aligns with current neuroscientific accounts of learning and neuroplasticity. Our aim is twofolds: first, to synthesize why and how Montessori practices appear to outperform traditional early-childhood models on outcomes spanning attention, memory, self-regulation, creativity, and social cognition; second, to situate these practices within an evidence based that clarifies the underlying mechanisms rather than merely contrasting „which is better.“ In doing so, we also engage recent school reforms in Slovakia and the Czech Republic, suggesting that policy makers and reform authors may benefit from an alternative, science-grounded perspective, even when it entails a paradigm shift in longstanding assumptions about teaching and learning.

1 Beyond Transmission: Education as a Mechanism of Neural Adaptation

Education, rooted in the Latin *educere*, literally meaning „to lead out“, rather than merely „to transmit“, is best understood as a deliberately designed ecology of experience that tunes the developing brain. Converging evidence from developmental cognitive neuroscience shows that learning experiences are literally built into neural circuits, shaping attention, memory, self-regulation, and social cognition across the lifespan. Pedagogy therefore functions less like a neutral delivery system and more like a regulator of brain plasticity, calibrating children's capacity to adapt to novelty, to detect and correct errors, and to generate creative solutions.

A first locus of this calibration is the brain's error monitoring system, a core mechanism of adaptive cognitive control. Its function is to detect deviations between expected and actual outcomes, thereby signaling the need for behavioral adjustment. Central to this system is the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), often described as the brain's „warning light on the dashboard“. While the ACC does not itself resolve discrepancies, it broadcasts a signal that something is amiss, recruiting other neural systems for corrective action. This signal is instantiated within milliseconds as error-related negativity (ERN), a well-characterized electrophysiological marker that interrupts ongoing processing and reallocates attentional resources. Developmentally, the ACC undergoes significant structural and functional refinement during middle childhood, with corresponding increases in ERN amplitude between roughly six and twelve years of age (Kelly et al., 2009; Tamnes et al., 2013).

Importantly, the maturation of this system is not fixed but is shaped by the learning environment. Educational practices across the world differ substantially in how they construe error, effort, and achievement, and these pedagogical contingencies feed back into the neural mechanisms of monitoring. In traditional, test-oriented models, dominant in many national contexts, learning is organized around correct answers, grades, and external evaluation. Within such systems, the ability to track error (i. e., error

monitoring) is disproportionately recruited not to improve when mistakes are made, but following correct responses, reinforcing the salience of accuracy and success. By contrast, alternative pedagogies deliberately cultivate different neural signatures. Montessori education, widely implemented as an international alternative, emphasizes self-directed exploration, collaborative learning, and the use of multisensory, autocorrective didactic materials. Errors are framed not as failures but as integral feedback within the learning process (Montessori, 1966). Neurocognitive data mirror this orientation: in Montessori classrooms, error-related signals are more pronounced following incorrect responses, indicating a system tuned to treat mistakes as valuable information for adaptation and growth (Denervaud et al., 2020).

Memory offers another window into how education shapes the brain. Memory is not a single storehouse but more like a library with different sections: semantic memory, which organizes meaning like an encyclopedia, and episodic memory, which stores lived experiences like a diary. Montessori schooling encourages children to build encyclopedia-like semantic networks, which support flexible transfer of knowledge and the ability to make novel connections more freely (as this form of knowledge is not fixed in time and space). This has even been linked to structural asymmetries in the parahippocampal cortex, a memory-related brain region (Schetter et al., 2023). Traditional education, by contrast, leans more on diary-like episodic traces tied to specific test contexts, which can be accurate but less transferable. The difference matters because creativity relies on semantic memory's ability to recombine knowledge in new ways (Kenett & Faust, 2019). Montessori's emphasis on meaning over rote recall may thus lay stronger foundations for innovative thinking.

At a systems level, education also tunes the balance between brain networks. The brain can be imagined as a city of neighborhoods connected by roads. In childhood, these neighborhoods tend to work in isolation, like separate suburbs. With development, the „roads“ between them grow busier, supporting integrated and flexible communication across the brain. Montessori students show signs of this integration earlier, with higher system diversity, akin to having more cross-town traffic, and lower spatiotemporal diversity, which reflects more stable routes of communication (Zanchi et al., 2024). This was particularly true in networks for attention, self-control, movement, and the cerebellum. The pattern resembles a more adult-like brain „road map“, suggesting that pedagogy can accelerate or slow how flexibly the brain's neighborhoods connect (Grayson & Fair, 2017).

Social learning further illustrates this principle. Humans are natural imitators, but imitation is a double-edged sword: it allows us to learn culture quickly but can also lead to „overimitation“, or copying irrelevant details without thinking critically. Traditional schools, with their adult-led focus, tend to foster more overimitation, while Montessori classrooms, where younger children learn from older peers and collaboration is central, encourage what scientists call epistemic vigilance, selectively deciding what is worth copying (Décaillet et al., 2024). This difference may stem from how the brain's „social radar“: regions such as the temporoparietal junction and medial prefrontal cortex develops sensitivity not just to actions but to intentions and trustworthiness (Bitsch et al., 2018). In effect, Montessori education creates a peer-driven ecology that strengthens children's ability to question, evaluate, and balance conformity with independence.

Creativity emerges from the interplay of all these systems. It depends on the brain's ability to switch flexibly between three networks: the default mode network, which generates novel ideas like a „daydreaming engine“; the executive control network, which evaluates those ideas like an „editor“; and the salience network, which acts like a „conductor“, or „selector“, deciding when to shift between them (Beatty et al., 2023). Montessori education appears to foster this switching ability. Children in Montessori schools spend less time stuck in rigid default mode states and more time in fluid patterns of connectivity that support

divergent thinking (Duval et al., 2023). This aligns with behavioral studies showing higher creativity scores and problem-solving skills in Montessori students (Lillard & Else-Quest, 2006). By giving children freedom to explore, opportunities for trial and error, and environments rich in sensory engagement, Montessori education cultivates the very neural dynamics that underlie creativity.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that education is not just about transferring knowledge but about shaping the architecture and dynamics of the brain. The ways classrooms frame mistakes, structure memory, organize attention, and arrange social relations have cascading effects on children's ability to regulate themselves, adapt flexibly, and innovate. This is the essence of neuro-pedagogy: aligning educational practice with the biology of learning. Remarkably, Montessori anticipated many of these principles long before neuroscience could validate them.

However, this is not yet happening, and this is similar in other countries as well. Gaujard and Denervaud (2023) state that „Given the large number of scientific facts supporting the advantages of Montessori education over traditional pedagogy for school (and non-school) outcomes, social-emotional well-being, and creativity (Demangeon et al., 2023), it is surprising that school reform is slowly listening to this evidence.“ Just like in Switzerland, we can also ask why this is the case in Slovakia. We agree that, although we wish the best for our children, we are not prepared to change our habits and question our beliefs (Gaujard & Denervaud, 2023, p. 46). Changing the paradigm of thinking is not simple. It requires an in-depth understanding of the issue and the willingness to reconsider and change the current approach to something, in this case, education. This work follows the challenge posed by Gaujard and Denervaud (2023), who argue that science should study pedagogy beyond comparative studies. We should move away from the question „Is it better or worse?“ and instead focus on the question „How and why does it work?“. The research answering these questions has been described above and is still being carried out. In this article, we will attempt to analyze the characteristics of the Montessori system in relation to current findings in neuro-pedagogy (with an emphasis on principles of brain-compatible environments and learning) and also in relation to the laws of learning described by pedagogical psychology. The parallels we describe in the presented analysis may partially answer the question „How and why does it work?“.

2 Brain-Compatible Pedagogy: Theoretical Groundings and Practical Implications

Brain-compatible learning emphasizes psychological safety, meaningful content, autonomy, sufficient time for deep practice, enriched environments, immediate feedback, collaboration, mastery through repetition, purposeful movement, and sensory engagement (Petlák, Valábik, & Zajacová, 2009; Shvarts-Serebro et al., 2024). Modern neuroscience adds biological specificity; for example, movement upregulates neurotrophins and supports cerebellar-prefrontal coupling; sleep consolidates synaptic changes; repeated, self-initiated practice stabilizes distributed networks; and feedback that is proximal and diagnostic optimizes error-based learning and memory consolidation (Kandel, 2001 as cited in Adámek, 2014). In this light, schooling is a lever on neurodevelopmental trajectories: its routines and values entrain patterns of attention, memory, cognitive control, and social inference that extend well beyond the classroom.

The policy implication is not a blanket endorsement of any single model, but a call to align instructional design with mechanisms of neural adaptation. Systems that overweight evaluative control, compress time for exploration, or restrict movement and collaboration risk entraining context-bound memory strategies, heightened conformity pressures, and less flexible network dynamics. Conversely, environments that normalize error as information, cultivate peer learning, and extend time for self-directed, embodied practice appear to foster the neural preconditions for transfer, critical thinking, and creativity. The

remainder of this work takes up that challenge, situating concrete Montessori design choices within contemporary accounts of error monitoring, memory consolidation, network maturation, social learning, and creative cognition, with the aim of specifying actionable, brain-compatible principles for educational reform.

The need to reconsider current educational approaches is also driven by findings in brain research (Boleková et al., 2020; Petlák et al., 2011; Petlák, Valábik & Zajacová, 2009). Neurodidactics and neuro-pedagogy, according to Petlák, Valábik and Zajacová (2009, p. 11), address „the impact of neuroscientific findings on pedagogy and didactics and how learning and teaching can be adapted to these findings“. The central issue of neuro-pedagogy, as Adámek (2014) notes, is the how the brain learns. He cites Kandel's definition of learning as changes in neuronal synapses that occur concurrently with behavioral change (quoted in Adámek, 2014). Learning, therefore, is not possible without activity in the nervous system (Boleková et al., 2020). During the preschool years, more than 70% of synapses are formed, making this period especially significant for human development. Intellectual abilities depend not only on how many synapses exist but on how they are organized into efficient networks; although synapses continue to form and remodel across life, the greatest proliferation occurring early. The years up to age three are particularly sensitive. Consequently, family context matters greatly, and have been extensively studied. Additionally, home routines are of importance, as rapid synapse formation and overall brain maturation are closely tied to REM sleep, which is longest during early and preschool years (Rajović, 2018). Sleep plays a crucial role in memory consolidating memory traces and facilitating their transfer to long-term storage through synaptic mechanisms, including long-term potentiation in the hippocampus. Beyond sleep, synapses are also shaped by learning and experience. „The more connections there are between neurons, the more neural networks are created, making the brain more flexible and able to learn more easily – it becomes denser“ (Petlák, Valábik & Zajacová, 2009, p. 21). Family environment and daily routines are of importance (i.e., sleep, food, qualitative social interactions), but similar emphasis should be placed on school contexts and routines, where, as children grow, an increasing share of their waking learning takes place.

If learning is to be effective, it should occur in a brain-compatible environment. Brain-compatible learning means translating knowledge about the structure and function of the brain into the design of teaching and learning. Neuro-pedagogy and neuro-didactics are attracting increasing attention as part of a broader effort to modernize educational science. As Petlák, Valábik, and Zajacová (2009, p. 11) put it, neuro-didactics and neuro-pedagogy address „the impact of neuroscientific knowledge on pedagogy and didactics and how learning and teaching can be adapted to these findings“. Neuro-pedagogy (also called neuroeducation or educational neuroscience) is an interdisciplinary field integrating neuroscience, psychology, and education (Shvarts-Serebro, et al., 2024). According to Adámek (2014), its central question is how the brain functions so we can understand how to teach it.

In the context of Montessori education, as well as pedagogy more generally, the crucial issue is the kind of environment we can provide to children based in light of insights from neuro-pedagogy and neuro-didactics. Comparative work on alternative pedagogies and neuro-pedagogy (and neuro-didactics) suggests that the principles and „rules“ for organizing a brain-compatible environment for learning were already articulated by Montessori.

A brain-compatible environment translate neurobiological principles into everyday classroom practice. Across authors (e.g., Zelina, 2000; Tóthová, Kostrub & Ferková, 2017), recurring design features include: psychological safety and trust; meaningful content; freedom of choice; uninterrupted working time; an enriched environment; immediate, informative feedback; collaboration; mastery through structured practice; purposeful movement; and multisensory engagement.

3 Theoretical Foundations of the Analysis

First, we outline the didactic principles of Montessori education (Zelinková, 1997), which serve as the starting point for our analysis. We then relate these principles to neuro-pedagogy, specifically, brain-compatible environments and learning, as well as to the laws of learning described in pedagogical psychology.

- **Respecting Sensitive Periods:** A core Montessori principle is to respect the child's sensitive periods. This applies both to adult-child interactions and to preparation of the environment. Careful observation is essential. Activities, materials, and adult approaches should be adapted to the child's current interests and developmental stage.
- **Progressivity / Developing Interests:** The organization of the environment and instructional actions should appropriately anticipate the child's development. Materials in the child's surroundings should stimulate growing interest, guiding the child forward and supporting ongoing development.
- **Creating Simple Logical Structures:** The environment and pedagogy should not be chaotic or confusing. Everything must be prepared in a way that is accessible and understandable to the child. The aim is to support the child's interest and remove obstacles to its fulfillment. Isolating salient properties within materials enables structured, non-chaotic acquisition of knowledge, skills, and abilities without distracting, irrelevant stimuli.
- **Rich Provision of Materials and Opportunities for Self-Development:** An environment rich in well-chosen materials encourages activity. Materials should be arranged to invite engagement and spark curiosity. Goals should be visible and understandable to the child. The richness of the offer ensures varied, high-quality, developmentally supportive stimuli, but it should not be excessive; order and system are essential.
- **Freedom of Choice and Movement:** An optimally prepared environment allows children to choose activities independently, move freely, and be encouraged in such behavior. Adults and the environment grant freedom rather than restricting choice and movement. The adult helps the child select materials and understand their purpose. The self-correcting nature of Montessori didactic materials plays a crucial role, allowing children to treat mistakes as information-feedback without emotional bias (Denervaud et al., 2020).
- **Age Appropriateness:** The quantity, size, and weight of materials must suit the child's age and physical abilities. Children should be able to manipulate materials independently, without adult assistance. This principle supports autonomy and the ability to work and develop (Zelinková, 1997).
- **Sensory Engagement:** Sensory engagement is embedded in all the principles above and is a defining feature of Montessori didactic materials. Children learn best through direct experience and active use of all senses. This approach strengthens the ability to recognize, categorize, and analyze information through tactile, visual, auditory, gustatory, and olfactory perception. Montessori materials are designed to stimulate sensory development, helping children understand and internalize abstract concepts through concrete, multi-sensory experiences.

4 Analysis of Montessori Education in Relation to Neuro-Pedagogy

For clarity, we provide a table (below) that highlights connections between key characteristics of Montessori education and principles of a brain-compatible learning environment, supported by established laws of learning. We then elaborate on these connections in detail.

Table 1: Alignment of Montessori Education with Neuroeducational Principles

Montessori Principles	Brain-Compatible Principles	Analysis of Connections and Similarities	Laws of Learning (Pedagogical Psychology)
Respect for Sensitive Periods	Age-Appropriate, Trust, Mastery	Montessori respects biologically conditioned periods of heightened sensitivity – neuroscience talks about brain plasticity, which is highest during these periods. A safe environment supports learning when the child experiences trust and security.	Law of Motivation (child is naturally motivated during sensitive periods), Law of Transfer (new knowledge builds on the child's readiness).
Progressivity / Developing Interests	Meaningful Content, Freedom of Choice	Montessori tracks the child's interest as the main driver of learning. Neuroscience confirms that interest activates the dopamine system, strengthening memory and learning.	Law of Motivation (internal motivation is the strongest), Law of Transfer (learning is meaningful when it builds on prior interests).
Creating Simple Logical Structures	Meaningful Content, Enriched Environment	Montessori materials are designed to allow children to create order and categorize – aligning with the neurobiological needs of the brain to organize information into meaningful wholes.	Law of Repetition (repetition of sorting creates knowledge), Law of Transfer (child transfers knowledge to other situations).
Rich Offer of Materials and Opportunities for Self-Development	Enriched Environment, Trust, Cooperation	Montessori environments provide visual, tactile, and cognitive stimuli – supporting synapse formation and the connection of brain areas. Trust and relationships reduce stress, making learning more effective.	Law of Motivation (availability and choice increase engagement), Law of Repetition (materials allow for repetition).
Freedom of Choice and Movement	Freedom of Choice, Targeted Movement, Trust	Montessori emphasizes autonomy and physical activity – neuroscience confirms that movement stimulates neuroplasticity and supports the creation of BDNF ³ (Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor). Freedom of choice increases motivation.	Law of Motivation (autonomy strengthens internal motivation), Law of Repetition (freedom allows for repetition at one's own pace).
Age Appropriateness	Trust, Mastery, Sensory Engagement	Montessori respects what the child can do at a certain age – similar to neuroscience and psychology, which talk about	Law of Transfer (new learning is linked to previously mastered knowledge), Law of Feedback

³ BDNF (Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor) is a brain growth factor that functions as a „fertilizer“ for nerve cells. It supports their growth, the creation of new connections, and the ability to adapt—precisely the processes that form the foundation of learning and memory. BDNF naturally increases when a child is active, exploring, learning with interest, and perceiving the learning process as meaningful. On the other hand, stress, monotonous sitting, or meaningless tasks reduce its production. Therefore, an environment where a child has the opportunity for movement, choice, and discovery – such as in Montessori education – is, from a neuro-scientific perspective, optimal for learning (Miranda et al. 2019).

		developmental stages. Materials correspond to current abilities and lead to mastery.	(materials provide immediate feedback).
Sensory Engagement	Purposeful movement, Sensory Engagement	Montessori emphasizes learning through the senses and movement – neuroscience confirms that multisensory stimulation and purposeful motor activity improve attention and support cognitive functions. Direct experience and hands-on activity accelerate the formation of neural connections.	Law of motivation (sensory stimuli enhance intrinsic interest in learning), Law of transfer (sensory experiences lay the foundation for abstract understanding).

Source: author's own elaboration based on the references used in the text

The key concept in our analysis is neuro-pedagogy, which, for our purposes, is defined as creating a brain-compatible environment for learning (Zelina, 2000; Tóthová, Kostrub & Ferková, 2017):

1. Trust: Trust and a sense of certainty and safety are cultivated by the educator. When learners feel comfortable and unthreatened, dopamine release supports learning and sustained attention. In Montessori settings, children are pressured by performance or time constraints; they work at their own pace and in line with their needs and interests, which reduces stress and promotes positive feelings. This climate is reinforced by families and the broader caregiving context.

2. Meaningful content: Montessori system is divided into five core areas: Language, Mathematics, Culture, Sensorial Education, and Practical Life. The curriculum is relevant to life in society, intrinsically interesting to children, and presented through aesthetically designed, self-correcting materials.

3. Freedom of choice: Children in Montessori education freely choose activities, materials, movement within the space, and how they allocate their time. „Freedom is not the ultimate goal, but a long process through which the child can acquire the human qualities of a free being“ (Poussin, 2017, p. 64). Choices align with children's sensitive periods and lived experiences.

4. Sufficient time: Montessori classrooms do not use bells or fixed 45-minute blocks. The organization does not adhere to the traditional class-hour system. Children manage their own work. Sufficient time for children to work with materials allows them to focus attention and delve into the details of working with the materials. The child develops sustained attention and the ability to focus. including time to notice, work with, and learn from mistakes.

5. Enriched environment: A rich offer of well-ordered materials invites activity. Materials are arranged to motivate engagement and curiosity, with clear, visible goals. The prepared environment is tailored for children to naturally fulfill their neurodevelopmental needs, paced through sensitive periods, and intrinsic interests, supporting motivation and transfer without overwhelming them.

6. Immediate feedback: Many materials are self-correcting, so errors generate prompt, informative feedback. As Stránský (2024) writes, making mistakes engages the brain in searching for solutions, examining, and learning by comparison; error is evidence that the brain is learning.

7. Collaboration: Pair and group work, as well as child-adult collaboration, are integral. Trusting relationships further reduce stress and enhance learning. According to Petlák et al. (2011), the brain favors

social learning: through cooperation, communication, and reasoned argumentat, learners acquire knowledge more effectively, including by observing, imitating, and analyzing other's behavior.

8. Mastery of content: Mastery entails using what has been learned in practical life and, ultimately, being able to teach it to others, as noted by Kovalik and Olsen. Montessori supports mastery through repetition and regular application beyond school, i.e., real-life activities even outside of school.

9. Purposeful movement: The hand is the instrument of the mind. Everything taught in Montessori education is processed through the hands and movement so learning is embodied; activities are designed to engage movement and fine motor control as part of cognition

10. Engagement of the senses: Montessori education places great emphasis on sensory perception as inseparable from learning. Children engaged in hands-on activities engage as well all their senses – sight, hearing, touch, smell, and taste. The didactic materials developed by Montessori let children explore and experiment properties such as color, shape, size, weight, and sound. This strengthens categorization, abstract understanding, motor skills, and concentration, laying foundations for later abstract thinking and problem-solving.

At the same time, Montessori education aligns with laws of learning articulated in educational psychology. Whether children are acquiring and improving various competencies (theirs or someone else's), or developing cognitive, psychomotor, and socio-emotional skills, learning follows robust regularities (Vendel, 2012; Linhartová, 2006). The process of learning is subject to the laws of learning. The Law of Motivation: holds that intrinsic motives best sustain learning. The brain needs to have an interest in learning. The Law of Feedback: For learning, it is important for children to receive informative feedback about their performance, so they can adjust quickly. Children need information about whether they are progressing correctly and whether the task/knowledge has been properly acquired. According to Petlák et al. (2009), learning is meaningless without feedback. When the brain receives feedback as soon as possible, it can correct or confirm the information more easily. The Law of Transfer: Transfer is the process where previously learned behaviors (knowledge, skills) influence the learning of other behaviors (knowledge, skills). The Law of Repetition underscores that spaced, varied practices strengthens neural circuits and consolidates learning; the more often circuits are activated, the stronger and more stable they become (Petlák, Valábik, & Zajacová, 2009), an essential aspect of deep knowledge. Repetition requires being systematic and following psycho-hygiene.

5 Contrasting Traditional and Brain-Compatible Education: A Brief Analysis

Based on the theoretical analysis of the description of Montessori education, brain-compatible environments (neuropedagogy), and the laws of learning from the perspective of pedagogical psychology (as well as the research presented above), we can consider Montessori education as an example of the practical application of neuropedagogical knowledge and principles. We believe that Montessori, based on (1) careful observation of children, (2) her medical degree, (3) experience working with children with various degrees of special educational needs, identified the principles and laws of „scientific pedagogy“ (Montessori, 1966), which, at the time of its creation, already respected and applied principles that today we rediscover under the name of neuropedagogy. The difference is that today we draw from different research opportunities regarding learning and the child's brain. This may sound somewhat bold, but the analysis shows that what we are now discovering as brain-compatible environments and principles of brain-based learning, based on research about the brain and learning, is a renaissance of what Montessori applied in her work with children

over a century ago. At the same time, as we have indicated above, there is a growing need for the transformation of the education system in Slovakia (and other countries). In Slovakia, there are regular efforts for educational reforms, but despite this, the country consistently ranks below average in PISA tests. Why might this be the case? Traditional education does not respect new findings in the area of brain learning that we have discussed above. In the following table, we provide a brief overview of what we can identify as the pitfalls or shortcomings of the traditional educational system.

Table 2: Traditional vs. Neuroeducation – Key Differences

Traditional Element	In contrast to...	Why is this a problem for the brain?
Curricula rigidly set by age	Sensitive periods, freedom of choice, meaningfulness	Children learn the „same“ things at the same time—regardless of readiness, interest, or pace.
Class-hour system (45-minute blocks)	Sufficient time, targeted movement	Learning is artificially interrupted; the brain needs continuity, integration, and time to process.
Front-facing teaching (teacher = main source of knowledge)	Enriched environment, meaningful content, collaboration	The child is a passive recipient; active learning (constructivism) stimulates more areas of the brain.
Minimal movement	Targeted movement, sensory engagement	Static sitting hinders blood circulation and neuroplasticity; movement is crucial for memory and concentration.
Feedback via grades (delayed, evaluative)	Immediate feedback	Grades motivate from the outside (not internally); they are often evaluative, not developmental.
Focus on performance, not process	Trust, perfect mastery	Children learn for the test or reward, not for understanding; the brain tends to push out learned material without connections.

Source: Author’s own elaboration

The analysis does not aim to reject traditional education. Our goal is to inform and inspire the reader to consider the possibilities of stimulating not only the child's personality in light of current knowledge in the field of neuro-pedagogy and learning. We also seek to highlight opportunities to enhance traditional education through new approaches informed by contemporary research in neuroscience and education.

6 Implications

Education is not a pipeline for facts; it is an ecology that sculpts living, plastic tissue. When time, space, materials, feedback, and relationships are organized, the result is not simply the delivery of content but the calibration of error signals, the stabilization of memories, the tuning of network dynamics, and the shaping of social inferences that will guide learning across the lifespan. Pedagogy, in this light, functions as a regulator of neural adaptation.

From this perspective, the debate about „methods“ becomes overly narrow. The real question is structural: which routines entrain which brain states, and toward what ends? Is the fuel success or pleasure/curiosity? Are teachers experiencing joy and embracing humanity? Indeed, what is true for students may also hold for their teachers. Classrooms are reciprocal ecosystems in which neural and behavioral dynamics reverberate between children and adults. Just as students’ brains are shaped by pedagogical structures, teachers’ brains are continuously sculpted by the same routines, stressors, and feedback loops. Mirroring effects mean that conditions fostering curiosity, autonomy, and resilience in learners also sustain

these qualities in educators; conversely, environments dominated by surveillance, evaluative control, and time compression risk dysregulation on both sides of the relationship. This reciprocity underscores a profound chicken-and-egg dilemma: do rigid, stress-inducing systems first exhaust teachers, who then transmit rigidity to their students, or do inflexible expectations imposed on learners erode teachers' sense of efficacy and vitality? Likely both processes reinforce one another. The rising prevalence of teacher burnout and attrition can be interpreted not only as a labor-market problem but also as evidence of unhealthy brain dynamics within educational systems. A truly brain-compatible pedagogy must therefore attend to teachers as well as students, creating conditions where both can engage, adapt, and thrive within a shared ecology of learning.

Classrooms that normalize error as information, protect uninterrupted periods of concentration, distribute authority across peers, and embed movement and sensory exploration are not merely humane; they cultivate distinct cognitive and neural profiles. Conversely, systems that compress exploration, externalize motivation, and delay diagnostic feedback entrain less flexible control strategies and context-bound memories. These are not matters of ideology but of mechanism.

Montessori education can be understood as a design proof: a century-old instantiation of principles that contemporary neuroscience is only now systematically validating. At the same time, intellectual honesty requires openness: no single model can claim a monopoly on neuroplasticity. The essential criterion is the alignment between developmental needs and instructional affordances. Whether in Steiner's emphasis on imagination, project-based learning's authentic inquiry, or other emergent pedagogies, the challenge is to design environments that respect sensitive periods, leverage intrinsic motivation, and provide feedback at the appropriate grain of learning.

The implication for policy is one of precision. Schooling should be evaluated in the same way as engineering: by how effectively inputs produce the desired state changes. This entails supporting designs that (a) surface and use errors as immediate feedback, (b) preserve extended blocks for deep practice, (c) integrate purposeful movement into cognition, (d) promote peer teaching and epistemic vigilance, and (e) prioritize meaning over performance signals. These are not rhetorical aspirations but operational parameters for a plastic system.

For researchers, the agenda must move beyond the question of „which is better?“ to the more generative questions of how and why. This requires coupling classroom microdesigns with mechanistic readouts; behavioral, physiological, and neural, and tracking developmental trajectories over time. The appropriate unit of analysis is not the lesson in isolation but the learner embedded within an ecosystem, where pedagogical choices modulate error monitoring, memory consolidation, network integration, and social reasoning in concert.

For practitioners, the imperative is iterative design. Classrooms should be treated as living laboratories: instrumented with rapid, formative feedback; co-designed with students; supported by self-correcting materials; structured to allow sustained work cycles; and choreographed to integrate purposeful movement. Incremental refinements (e. g., shorter feedback loops, richer peer models, and clearer affordances) aggregate into qualitative shifts in how minds organize themselves.

For educational leaders, the challenge is courage. Reform will falter if it continues to privilege test scores while neglecting the mechanisms that underpin them. The central criterion should be transfer: the capacity of graduates to generalize, self-correct, collaborate, and innovate under conditions of uncertainty. Schedules, assessments, and teacher preparation should be realigned with this aim. Where policy restricts the conditions for plasticity, curriculum alone cannot compensate.

Finally, for all of us, humility is essential. The brain remains generative, context-sensitive, and only partially understood. The prudent stance is pluralistic and empirical: preserve practices that reliably foster adaptive intelligence, abandon those that constrain it, and remain open to experimentation at the margins.

If such principles were taken seriously, schools would look profoundly different. Education would be designed for plasticity rather than coverage; progress would be measured in adaptability rather than recall; time would be treated as a primary resource; error would serve as a teacher rather than a stigma; and responsibility would be entrusted to children, not only as a moral imperative but as a neurobiological catalyst. Education, understood beyond transmission, remains the most powerful lever for shaping the future; because it literally shapes the brains that will create it.

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